

Studies on the Preparation and Characterisation of Bis-*p*-biphenyltin(IV) Carboxylates

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Bis-*p*-biphenyltin(IV) carboxylates of the type $p-(C_6H_5-C_6H_4)_2Sn(OCOR)_2$, where $R = o-CH_3-C_6H_4$, $p-CH_3-C_6H_4$, $CH_3-O-C_6H_4$, $CH_2-C_6H_5$ and $CH=CHC_6H_5$, have been prepared by the reaction of bis-*p*-biphenyltin dichloride with sodium salt of respective carboxylic acid in 1 : 2 molar ratio in methanol and acetone mixture. The complexes are characterised by elemental analysis, molecular weight determination, conductivity measurements, infrared and 1H nmr spectroscopy. The carboxylate moiety acts as bidentate in these complexes.

ORGANOTIN carboxylates of the three known types, viz. $R_3SnOCOR'$, $R_2Sn(OCOR')_2$ and $RSn(OCOR')_3$ are of great commercial value owing to their utility as polyvinyl chloride stabilisers¹⁻⁵ and fungicides⁶. Their structural chemistry is also of great interest because of the varying bonding behaviour of the carboxylate moiety in different organotin carboxylates. Extensive structural investigations using ir, 1H nmr, Mössbauer spectroscopy and X-ray studies made on triorganotin carboxylates, $R_3SnOCOR$, suggest that most of such compounds occur in the solid phase as coordination polymers with pentacoordinate tin⁷⁻¹¹. In solution or in the liquid phase, the compounds are monomeric. Formation of the polymeric structure is also impeded by the steric hindrance presented by bulky R group or a branching R' group. Furthermore, in dialkyltin carboxylates, $R_2Sn(OCOR')_2$, the tin atom has been suggested to bear coordination number of six with the distorted *trans* arrangement of the alkyl groups and the carboxylate moiety acting as a bidentate ligand^{12,13}.

The present communication deals with the synthesis and structural investigation of some hitherto unknown carboxylates of bis-*p*-biphenyltin(IV) of the type $(p-C_6H_5-C_6H_4)_2Sn(OCOR)_2$, where $R = o-CH_3-C_6H_4$, $p-CH_3-C_6H_4$, $CH_3-O-C_6H_4$, $CH_2-C_6H_5$ and $CH=CH-C_6H_5$.

Experimental

All reagents were of AnalaR grade. Bis-*p*-biphenyltin(IV) dichloride was prepared by the disproportionation reaction of tetrakis-*p*-biphenyltin(IV) and tin tetrachloride¹⁴.

Preparation of sodium salt of carboxylic acids : Sodium salt of carboxylic acids used in this work, were synthesised according to the preparation of sodium cinnamate. Sodium hydroxide pellets (4 g, 0.1 mol) were taken in ethanol (50 ml) and

refluxed till it dissolved completely. Cinnamic acid (14.8 g, 0.1 mol) was taken in dry benzene (50 ml). Alkali solution was added slowly dropwise to the acid solution till it showed pink colour with phenolphthalein. The sodium salt of cinnamic acid was precipitated out and filtered. The precipitate was washed several times with ether and dried.

Preparation of complexes. Biscinnamatobis(*p*-biphenyltin(IV)) : To a solution of sodium cinnamate (3.4 g, 0.02 mol) in methanol (50 ml) was added a solution of bis-*p*-biphenyltin dichloride (4.95 g, 0.01 mol) in acetone (50 ml). The mixture was refluxed for 0.5 h and filtered. Solvent was removed from the filtrate under reduced pressure to 10 ml and then petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) was added dropwise. A white precipitate formed was collected, dried *in vacuo* and recrystallised from a mixture of methylene chloride and petroleum ether (1 : 1) to give a white crystalline solid (80%).

Similarly other bis(*p*-biphenyltin) biscarboxylates, i.e. *o*-tolyl, *p*-tolyl, anisyl and benzyl were prepared. Analytical data for the complexes are given in Table 1.

Infrared spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 399 grating spectrophotometer using KBr pellets in the 4000-400 cm^{-1} region. Proton magnetic resonance spectra were recorded at ambient temperature (28°) at sweep width of 500 Hz with a Varian A-60 spectrometer. The magnetic field sweep was calibrated with a standard sample of chloroform and TMS (1%) in deuterated chloroform. Quantitative estimation of carbon and hydrogen was done by using micro-analytical apparatus. Tin was estimated as tin oxide gravimetrically.

Results and Discussion

The new bis-*p*-biphenyltin(IV) bis-carboxylates are obtained by the reaction of bis-*p*-biphenyltin dichloride with the respective sodium salt of

TABLE 1—CONDUCTIVITY AND ANALYTICAL DATA OF $(p\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4)_2\text{Sn}(\text{OCOR})_2$ COMPLEXES

Sl. no.	R	M.p. °C	Molar conductivity* $\Omega^{-1}\text{cm}^2\text{mol}^{-1}$	Mol. Wt. Found/(Calcd.)	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
					C	H	Sn
1.	<i>o</i> -CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	48-9°	0.65	702.4 (694.7)	68.5 (69.09)	4.4 (4.60)	18.4 (17.09)
2.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	89°	0.67	703.8 (694.7)	68.7 (69.09)	4.72 (4.60)	18.7 (17.09)
3.	CH ₃ O-C ₆ H ₄	80°	0.69	720.2 (726.7)	65.92 (66.06)	4.44 (4.40)	16.7 (16.34)
4.	CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	90°	0.80	700.6 (694.7)	69.23 (69.09)	4.58 (4.61)	17.62 (17.09)
5.	OH=CH C ₆ H ₄	72°	0.83	726.6 (718.7)	89.97 (70.13)	4.40 (4.45)	15.94 (16.52)

* Concentration was 0.5 m in each case.

carboxylic acid molar ratio 1 : 2 in acetone-methanol mixture according to the following equation,

The complexes are white crystalline solids and are fairly stable in dry and inert atmosphere. Conductance measurements and molecular weight determinations show that all the complexes are essentially non-electrolytes in nitrobenzene and are monomeric in benzene.

Infrared spectra : In the infrared spectra, the study of the region 1700-1300 cm^{-1} incorporating (OCO) stretching vibrations is of great diagnostic value. In this region, the difference between $\nu_{\text{asym}}(\text{OCO})$ and $\nu_{\text{sym}}(\text{OCO})$ may be taken as good criterion to identify the particular mode of bonding of the carboxylate ligand¹⁵. If this difference is of the order of $\sim 150\text{ cm}^{-1}$, the carboxylate moiety may be considered to act either as bridging or as bidentate ligand¹⁶. However, a difference greater than 200 cm^{-1} indicates the monodentate behaviour of the ligand¹⁷.

The ir spectral data of all the compounds studied in the present investigation (Table 2) reveal them to be having bidentate carboxylate ligands because the difference between $\nu_{\text{asym}}(\text{OCO})$ and $\nu_{\text{sym}}(\text{OCO})$ is of the order $\sim 150\text{ cm}^{-1}$, thereby a coordination number of six may be assigned to tin atom.

TABLE 2—CHARACTERISTIC IR BANDS (cm^{-1}) OF $(p\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4 - \text{C}_6\text{H}_4)_2\text{Sn}(\text{OCOR})_2$ COMPLEXES

Sl. no.	R	$\nu_{\text{asym}}(\text{OCO})$	$\nu_{\text{sym}}(\text{OCO})$	$(\nu_{\text{asym}} - \nu_{\text{sym}})$
1.	<i>o</i> -CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	1600s	1480s	120
2.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	1610vs	1480s	130
3.	CH ₃ O-C ₆ H ₄	1600vs	1480s	120
4.	CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	1550vs	140s	130
5.	OH=CH C ₆ H ₄	1575s	1430s	145

* s = strong, vs = very strong.

¹H nmr spectra : Proton magnetic resonance spectra of the bis-*p*-biphenyltin(IV) carboxylates show two types of signals, and correlation of the

resonance signals with various groups present in the molecules has been made. The spectra exhibit the resonance signal in the form of a doublet, triplet and doublet between τ 2.0 and 3.0 due to biphenyl protons. The other proton signals characterising different carboxylate groups are a singlet due to CH₃ protons attached to benzene moiety of carboxylate $\tau \sim 7.6$ and a singlet due to C₆H₄ proton $\tau \sim 2.8$, in *o*-tolyl complexes. In *p*-tolyl complex, there is a singlet $\tau \sim 7.62$ due to CH₃ protons attached to benzene nuclei of the carboxylate and a singlet which is mixed with the other benzene protons of biphenyl unit $\tau \sim 2.44$. In the anisyl derivative, there appears a singlet $\tau \sim 6.15$ due to methoxy group and a singlet $\tau \sim 2.24$ due to benzene nuclei characterise the phenyl acetate complex. In cinnamate complex, there are two singlet $\tau \sim 3.4$ and 3.6 whereas proton signals due to benzene ring of cinnamate mixed with the protons of the benzene ring of biphenyl unit.

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